

Branched saturated esters and diesters. Sustainable synthesis of excellent biolubricants.

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Highlights:

Fifteen new branched esters are obtained through an enzymatic solvent-free process.

The viscosity index shows that three of the obtained esters are excellent biolubricants.

These double branched esters can be successfully produced at 80 °C and 5 % wt. catalyst.

Conversions above 95 % are obtained in less than 3.5 hours of reaction.

Other double branched esters could be synthesized using the proposed procedure.

ABSTRACT

The enzymatic production of biolubricants with desirable properties such as high viscosity index and resistance to oxidation is investigated. These characteristics are ascribed to their branched structure and high molecular weight, as well as, to the absence of unsaturated bonds in the molecule. Solvent-free processes with moderate enzyme concentrations (up to 5 % wt.) and reaching conversions of 95 % or more, have been conducted.

Firstly, up to fifteen branched esters and diesters, all of them saturated, are obtained from a branched acid, 2-methylhexanoic acid, and a variety of linear and branched

alcohols and linear diols. Among them, three esters have viscosity indexes close to 200 or higher (1,10-decanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate, 1,12-dodecanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate and 2-octyl-1-dodecanoyl 2-methylhexanoate). For the synthesis of these compounds, optimization of biocatalyst concentration and temperature has been carried out, reaching conversions above 95 % within operation times between 2 and 3.5 hours.

1.- Introduction.

Lubricants are widely used in different industries, including automotive, manufacturing, aerospace, and much more. Traditional lubricants are often derived from petroleum sources and are known as mineral-oil-based lubricants. Due to the growing concern for environmental conservation and the relentless depletion of oil reserves, the development of biolubricants has been rapidly expanding in recent years [1].

These biolubricants, derived from renewable resources, are biodegradable, non-toxic and do not persist in the environment for extended periods [2]. Among them, vegetable oils have also other desirable advantages such as excellent lubricating power and high viscosity index [3]. Nonetheless, even when the majority of commonly used non-edible plant oils possess favorable lubricating qualities, they fail to fully meet the performance standards usually required for industrial lubricants. The abundance of unsaturated fatty acids in these plant oils contributes to their fluidity at lower temperatures, while double bonds, particularly at high concentrations, renders these oils susceptible to oxidation [4]. On the contrary, excessive saturation level in the oil leads to inadequate low-temperature characteristics.

All these performance constraints of lubricating with plant oils can be overcome through chemical modification, which is the most promising technique so far [5]. The main focus of chemical modifications lies in altering the acyl and alkoxy functional groups, as well as the double bonds present in the oil. Esterification or transesterification reactions are widely employed to produce esters, making it one of the most frequent procedures. This kind of esters demonstrates superior lubrication characteristics compared to their plant-oil or triacylglycerol counterparts due to the polarity of ester groups, which facilitates

their durable adhesion to metal surfaces resulting in the formation of exceptional protective layers or films with lubricating properties. Additionally, these esters exhibit enhanced performance at lower temperatures, as well as higher flash points, reduced volatility, and improved resistance to oxidation, compared to the corresponding plant oils [2].

Mineral acids such as hydrochloric (HCl), sulfuric (H₂SO₄) or p-toluenesulfonic acid (C₇H₈O₃S) are used as catalysts in esterification and transesterification processes. However, these processes come with certain limitations, such as challenges in isolating the desired products and the corrosive nature of the strong-acid catalysts. To overcome these issues and ensure complete conversion, basic catalysts like calcium oxide (CaO) are also employed. Nevertheless, the activation and regeneration of the catalyst necessitate high temperatures [6]. As an alternative, lipases have gained recognition as eco-friendly catalysts suitable for numerous industrial applications. They offer several advantages, including their ability to exhibit high catalytic activity under mild reaction conditions. Additionally, lipases demonstrate exceptional selectivity, preventing the formation of unwanted byproducts. In the literature there are many papers where the production of biolubricants using free or immobilized lipases from different sources is described. These publications have been thoroughly examined and consolidated in two recent comprehensive reviews [7, 8].

The types of acids and alcohols employed in the esterification and transesterification procedures have a direct impact on the physical, chemical, and lubricating properties of biolubricants. In general, vegetable oils are used as feedstock and then a dual transesterification process is performed. Firstly, monoalkyl esters are generated using short-chain alcohols (methanol or ethanol). Then, this is followed by the transesterification of those monoalkyl esters by using mono- or poly- alcohols [7]. Although less common, other researchers choose to use free fatty acids that, in greater or lesser proportions, are present in natural oils or those formed after the hydrolysis of triglycerides, as the base for the synthesis of biolubricants.

Table 1 shows different publications describing biocatalytic synthesis of esters with application as biolubricants using free fatty acids as substrates of enzymatic reactions. All of the proposed processes used branched alcohols because their presence into the

ester molecule leads to improved biolubricant performance. Furthermore, the linear hydrocarbon component of the acid contributes to a favorable viscosity index, resulting in a lower pour point [2, 32]. It is also known that lubricant properties of these esters under low temperature significantly improve when branching is present in the acid moiety or when both, the acid and alcohol, are branched [33]. However, not many papers can be found in the literature in which the acid moiety of the ester is a branched acid, because the esterification of those acids using lipases as catalysts is not free of problems. The cosmetic ingredient cetyl 2-ethylhexanoate is a well-known example of branched ester attempted to be obtained by enzymatic synthesis, even so with no success. Exclusively, appreciable conversions were achieved only by using solvent (hexane), catalyst concentrations above 250 % and process times longer than 60 hours [34]. Efforts to esterify a branched acid with a branched alcohol to obtain 2-ethylhexyl 2-ethylhexanoate, another well-known cosmetic ingredient, can also be found in the literature [35]. In this case, supercritical carbon dioxide was used as solvent, which facilitates the product purification, even so, the achieved conversions did not exceed 80 %. All of this gives an idea of how difficult esterifying branched acids using enzymes as catalysts is, which can be explained by the mechanism of the reaction and the structure of the active center of these enzymes. Some authors suggest that *Candida antarctica* lipase has difficulties in accepting branched carboxylic acids into its active center, in studies where attempts to increase its affinity for 2-ethylhexanoic acid have been unsuccessful [36]. Hence, currently, it is essential to employ conventional chemical synthesis techniques involving acidic catalysts and elevated temperatures.

The aim of this work is to exploit the environmental advantages of the synthesis of branched fatty acid esters using lipases in solvent-free conditions, resulting in high purity products, which can be labeled as "natural" and do not require costly purification steps. Instead of further attempting the esterification of 2-ethylhexanoic acid, already proved to be unproductive, a systematic search for new esters derived from 2-methylhexanoic acid is presented [37]. Lipases have more affinity for this branched acid and the obtained esters are then branched. In addition, if the alcohol is branched too, the resulting esters will be doubly branched, just like those obtained from diols.

2.- Materials and methods.

2.1. Chemicals.

All substrates, 2-methylhexanoic acid ($\geq 99\%$), 1-octanol ($\geq 98\%$), 1-dodecanol ($\geq 98\%$), 1-tetradecanol ($\geq 99\%$), 1-hexadecanol ($\geq 99\%$), 2-ethyl-1-hexanol ($\geq 99.6\%$), 3,5,5-trimethyl-1-hexanol ($\geq 85\%$), 3,7-dimethyl-1-octanol ($\geq 98\%$), 2-butyl-1-octanol ($\geq 95\%$), 2-hexyl-1-decanol ($\geq 97\%$), 2-octyl-1-dodecanol ($\geq 97\%$), neopentyl glycol (99%), trimethylolpropane ($\geq 98\%$), 1,5-pentanediol ($\geq 96\%$), 1,6-hexanediol ($\geq 97\%$), 1,10-decanediol ($\geq 98\%$) and 1,12-dodecanediol ($\geq 99\%$), were supplied by Merck. Lipozyme[®] 435 lipase was generously donated by Novozymes Spain S.A.

2.2. Reaction conditions.

In all cases the esterification reaction was carried out in a 50 mL glass-jacketed tank reactor (Vidra FOC 505/2), equipped with a vertical stirrer (IKA NANOSTAR 75). A total amount of 20 g of substrates in stoichiometric proportions were used and no solvent was added. In the preliminary assays a temperature of 70 °C, stirring speed of 350 rpm and an amount of enzyme of 2.5 % wt., were used. In the optimization experiments, biocatalyst concentration ranges from 1.25 to 5.0 % wt. and the temperature from 60 to 80 °C.

Reaction monitoring was carried out by measuring the acid value (AV) according to ASTM D964-02e at different times. The standard defines the acid value as the milligrams of potassium hydroxide (KOH) required to neutralize the free acids contained in one gram of sample. A Metrohm[®] Titrando 888 automatic potentiometric titrator was used for this determination.

From the acid value the conversion (%) is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Conversion} = \frac{AV_0 - AV_t}{AV_0} \times 100$$

where AV_0 is the initial acid value and AV_t is the acid value after a time t has elapsed since the addition of the catalyst.

Density and viscosity of all the prepared esters were measured with a DMA 5000M density meter/LOVIS 2000 M rolling-ball viscometer from Anton Paar. Measurements were performed at two temperatures, 40 ° and 100 °C.

3.- Results and discussion.

3.1. Esters of 2-methylhexanoic acid and linear mono-hydroxylated alcohol.

One of the objectives of this work is to study the influence of the size and nature of different alcohols on the reaction rate and the extent of esterification, as well as exploring the possibilities of synthesizing a collection of branched esters.

First, the results of the synthesis of branched esters from 2-methylhexanoic acid and different linear mono-hydroxylated alcohols are shown. The alcohols have a chain length between 8 and 16 carbon atoms, shorter chains were dismissed because of their high volatility, which would imply the use of different reaction strategies, as open-air reactors are used to allow removing the water produced during esterification.

The results of this experimental series are shown in Figure 1, which represents the evolution of the conversion with time. It can be seen that conversions close to 100 % are achieved after 4 h of reaction for all the alcohols. The lowest conversion is achieved when 1-octanol is used (approximately 95 %). This could be attributed to the greater volatility of this alcohol compared to alcohols containing a higher number of carbon atoms, leading to its partial evaporation from the reaction medium.

Therefore, the reaction rate is affected by the chain length, increasing slightly as the chain size increases. This behavior can be explained by two concurrent phenomena. On one hand, this effect can be explained by the fact that longer chain alcohols offer the enzyme a more hydrophobic environment. On the other hand, and since the reaction medium is only composed of the substrates in equimolecular amounts, alcohols of higher molecular weight represent a higher mass percentage, so the mass proportion of the acid is lower. This can be beneficial due to the fact that acids with a pKa of around 4.8 or lower negatively affect lipase activity with irreversible inactivation, as described in the literature [27], so this effect would be more significant the greater the amount of acid in the medium.

3.2. Esters of 2-methylhexanoic acid and branched mono-hydroxylated alcohol.

The esterification of 2-methylhexanoic acid with different branched alcohols has also been carried out, thereby obtaining doubly branched esters. As in the previous section,

only alcohols with a minimum of 8 carbon atoms and an appropriate low volatility to be used in an open vessel, have been studied here.

Figure 2 shows the results of the esterification of 2-methylhexanoic acid with three branched alcohols of 8, 9 and 10 carbon atoms. As can be seen, high conversions were reached in 3 h or less for all of them. In the case of 2-ethylhexanol, a slightly lower conversion was obtained because of its lowest boiling temperature, as in the previous series with the 1-octanol, where the alcohol evaporation prevents achieving total conversions.

Reaction rate is also lower for 2-ethylhexanol, while for alcohols of 9 and 10 carbon atoms are very similar and do not follow the same pattern as for the linear alcohol series. Here, it appears that the length and position of the alcohol side chains have the strongest influence on the rate of the process, covering up the possible influence of the total number of carbons. Shorter side chains and longer distance of them from the carbon holding the hydroxyl group provided higher reaction rates. This behavior can be explained by the fact that longer branches, or chains closer to the carbon with the -OH group, may hinder access to the active center of the lipase, as in the case of 2-ethylhexanol holding its side chain in C2.

The evolution of the synthesis of 2-methylhexanoic acid esters with branched alcohols of higher molecular weight (12, 16 and 20 carbon atoms) is shown below (Figure 3). Comparing with the previous figure, it can be seen that for heavier alcohols the reaction times are slightly longer, requiring more than 5 h to reach conversions close to 100 %. Hence, the trend is reversed with respect to linear alcohols, the larger the size, the slower the rate. However, in this case the size of the alcohol does not seem to be the critical factor, but the size of the side chain. In all three cases the side chain is located on the carbon adjacent to the one supporting the hydroxyl group. Side chains with a larger number of carbon atoms may make it more difficult for the alcohol to reach the active center of the enzyme.

It can be concluded that, in the esterification with branched alcohols, the predominant effect on the reaction rate is steric hindrance; the shorter the length of the branch, the higher the rate. In addition, considering the position of the branch, positions more distant from the hydroxyl group are observed to be more favorable.

3.3. Esters of 2-methyl hexanoic acid and linear di-hydroxylated alcohol.

Another possibility to obtain double branched esters could be the esterification of branched acids with linear diols or with branched polyols. Firstly, two branched alcohols have been tested: neopentyl glycol and trimethylolpropane, but esterifications with the chosen acid were not successful, as very long processes are not considered interesting from a practical point of view. For that reason, in this paper only the results for the synthesis of 2-methylhexanoic acid with four primary straight-chain diols of 5, 6, 10 and 12 carbon atoms have been presented and can be seen in Figure 4.

It can be observed that the four reactions evolve at a reasonable rate, reaching conversions above 95 % in 5 h. In the systems with diols of 5 and 6 carbon atoms the % wt. of acid in the reactor reaches values of about 70 % since substrate molar ratios of 1:1 are used in all cases. However, this high acid amount does not seem to affect the enzymatic activity. On the contrary, for diols of 5 and 6 carbon atoms the reaction proceeds faster than for diols of higher molecular weight (10 and 12 carbon atoms), for which the steric hindrance seems to be the main factor.

Comparing the reaction rate using diols of 5 and 6 carbon atoms, it can be observed that it is higher when 1,6 hexanediol is used as substrate. In this case the main factor does not seem to be the steric hindrance, but the hydrophobicity provided by alcohols with a longer chain length and the lower amount of acid in the reaction medium seem to be the effects with a greater weight in the reaction rate.

3.4. Characterization of esters as biolubricants.

One of the main characteristics to establish if a substance has a good lubricant performance is the viscosity index. The viscosity of a lubricant is actually its resistance to flow and shear and it can change with the temperature, the viscosity index is in fact the rate of the viscosity variations due to a temperature change, the higher its value the lowest the viscosity change. Its value has been determined according to ASTM D2270, based on density and dynamic and kinematic viscosities measurements at 40 and 100 °C. The ASTM standard includes different methodologies if the viscosity index of the substance is lower or higher than 100. Among the fifteen branched esters obtained in

this research, only four have a kinematic viscosity higher than 2 mm²/s at 100 °C and the abovementioned procedure can be applied. The final results are presented in Table 2.

Physicochemical properties of substances with lubricating characteristics are widely known and they have been reported in a number of studies [1]. Mineral oils have good oxidative stability, but their biodegradability is very limited, and their viscosity indexes are usually around 100. On the contrary, vegetable oils have much higher viscosity indexes and better biodegradability, but the presence of unsaturated fatty acid chains makes their oxidative stability rather poor. The esters obtained in this work get the best combination of both, they have high viscosity indexes and are saturated molecules, a characteristic that gives them high oxidative stability.

Table 3 summarizes some substances that can be used as lubricants and whose viscosity indexes have been reported by other authors. In view of the values, it seems that most lubricants that achieve high viscosity indexes have unsaturated chains in their structure, like soybean oil and its derived products, among others. As mentioned above, this can lead to less stability against oxidation. The only exceptions are di-2-ethylhexyl sebacate and di-2-ethylbutyl dodecanedioate, both of them are linear saturated dicarboxylic acids (sebacic and dodecanoic) esterified twice with branched alcohols, 2-ethylhexanol and 2-ethylbutanol, respectively, which result in esters with two branches in the same molecule [39]. Three of the four esters included in Table 2, in particular those with the highest viscosity index, are double branched, being two of them diesters obtained by esterification of a linear dialcohol with a branched acid at its two ends, and the other one a branched acid with a branched alcohol.

This evidence opens the door to the formulation, and enzymatic production, of many other double branched esters to be used as highly viscosity-index lubricants. Some examples might be the esterification of methyl hexanoic acid with other branched alcohols, or the use of dicarboxylic acids for esterification with branched alcohols.

The high viscosity index also seems to be related to the number of carbons in the ester as presented by Ahmed in 2015 [39] with 24-carbon diesters. This conclusion has been proved in the present paper where diesters with chain lengths between 24 and 27 carbon atoms have been obtained, being 2-octyl-1-dodecanoyl 2-methylhexanoate (27 carbon atoms) the one with the highest viscosity index (204.28).

3.5. Optimal reaction conditions for the biocatalytic synthesis of chosen esters.

Among the whole range of branched esters obtained in this work, three of them have excellent properties to be used as lubricants under extreme conditions (viscosity index close to 200 or even higher). Two of them belong to the diester group, obtained by the double esterification of a linear dialcohol linked to two branched acid molecules. These diesters have very high viscosity indexes, although less than 200. The third one belongs to the group of branched acid and branched alcohol esters. It has an exceptional viscosity index value above 200. These three esters have been selected for the optimization of their solvent-free enzymatic production.

The optimization follows a classical pattern, and the variables have been optimized independently, one by one. Experiments to determine the optimum temperature have been carried out with a constant biocatalyst concentration equal to 2.5 % wt. Figure 5 shows the optimization of the temperature for the three selected esters. Figure 5A corresponds to 1,10-decanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate, Figure 5B to 1,12-dodecanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate and Figure 5C to 2-octyl-1-dodecanoyl 2-methylhexanoate. It has been proved that the increase of the temperature has a positive influence on the reaction rate of all the three processes, so the choice of 80 °C as the operation temperature is justified by the significant improvement compared to 70 °C. In addition, the higher temperature also favors the removal of the water formed in the process from the reaction medium and does not seem to adversely affect the activity of the enzyme. Consequently, 80 °C has been selected as the optimum temperature and is the one used in the biocatalyst concentration optimization assays.

Figure 6 shows the optimization of the amount of enzyme for the three selected esters at 80 °C. Figure 6A corresponds to 1,10-decanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate, Figure 6B to 1,12-dodecanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate and Figure 6C to 2-octyl-1-dodecanoyl 2-methylhexanoate. It can be observed that the larger amount of enzyme (5 % wt.) is also the best option as for all the three esters the time required to achieve conversions above 95 % is substantially lower when increasing catalyst concentration from 2.5 % to 5 %.

Final decisions concerning experimental conditions should be made based on global economic and sustainability criteria, since it has been proved that all the studied esters can be successfully obtained by enzymatic synthesis. In general, 80 °C and 5 % wt.

concentration of the biocatalyst are considered to be acceptable conditions for obtaining these biolubricants in reasonable reaction times.

4. Conclusions.

Saturated branched esters have appropriate properties for their use as biolubricants under extreme temperatures. In this work, three esters with excellent lubricating properties have been synthesized: two of them are 17 and 19 carbon atoms diesters (obtained from dialcohol and branched acid), both with two methyl branches on the acid moiety and the third one consists of a branched acid esterified with a branched alcohol resulting in a 27 carbon atoms ester. All of these three esters are saturated compounds, which gives them high oxidation stability. Furthermore, the presence of double branching and their high molecular weight provides them with good lubricating behavior, which is partly evidenced by their high viscosity index.

Furthermore, this work opens a new way of obtaining other saturated esters with high viscosity indexes. It has been demonstrated the possibility of using enzymatic catalysis in the absence of solvents for the esterification of a branched acid, 2-methyl hexanoic acid, with other branched alcohols. These can have long side chains at the 2-position, resulting in esters with excellent lubricating properties and, more importantly, the specificity of the biocatalytic reaction, the absence of solvents and the high conversions achieved, guarantee that these processes are environmentally sustainable.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Fuensanta Máximo: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Supervision. **Josefa Bastida:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Supervision. **Claudia Montiel:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Supervision. **María Gómez:** Methodology, Writing – original draft, Validation, Formal analysis. **María Dolores Murcia:** Methodology, Writing – original draft, Validation, Formal analysis. **Cristina Barqueros:** Investigation, Methodology, Data curation, Formal analysis. **Salvadora Ortega-Requena:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Table 1.- Summarized publications describing the enzymatic synthesis of saturated branched esters (using free fatty acid as substrate).

Acid	Alcohol	Lipase	Reference
Adipic acid	2-ethylhexanol	Novozym [®] 435 Lipozyme [®] IM	[9]
Palmitic acid	2-ethylhexanol	Lipase <i>Candida</i> sp. 99-125	[10]
Sebacic acid	2-ethylhexanol 3,5,5-trimethylhexanol	Novozym [®] 435 Lipozyme [®] IM	[11]
Palmitic acid	2-ethylhexanol	Lipase <i>Candida</i> sp. 99-125	[12]
Myristic acid	Isopropyl alcohol	Lipase <i>Bacillus cereus</i> MTCC 8372	[13]
Palmitic acid	2-ethylhexanol	Novozym [®] 435	[14]
Palmitic acid	2-ethylhexanol	Lipozyme [®] RM IM	[15]
Valeric acid Caprylic acid Oleic acid	Trimethylolpropane (TMP)	Novozym [®] 435	[16]
Palmitic acid	2-ethylhexanol	CAL A	[17]
Caprylic acid	Trimethylolpropane (TMP)	Lipase <i>Candida</i> sp. 99-125	[18]
Caprylic acid	Trimethylolpropane (TMP)	Lipase <i>Candida</i> sp. 99-125	[19]
Oleic acid	3,7-di methyl 1-octanol 2-ethylhexanol	Callera Trans L	[20]
Palmitic acid	2-ethylhexanol	Lipase <i>Alcaligenes</i> sp QLM	[21]
Adipic acid	2-ethylhexanol	Novozym [®] 435	[22]
Adipic acid	Isononyl alcohol	Eversa [®] (TL)	[23]
Levulinic acid	Trimethylolpropane (TMP)	Novozym [®] 435	[24]
Azelaic acid	2-ethylhexanol	Novozym [®] 435	[25]
Palmitic acid Stearic acid	2-ethylhexanol	Novozym [®] 435 Novozym [®] 40086	[26]
Heptanoic acid	Neopentyl glycol (NPG)	Novozym [®] 435	[27]
Adipic acid Sebacic acid	2-ethylbutanol	Novozym [®] 435	[28]
Pelargonic acid Oleic acid	Trimethylolpropane (TMP)	Lipase <i>Candida</i> sp. 99-125 Novozym [®] 435	[29]
Capric/caprylic acid	Neopentyl glycol (NPG)	Lipozyme [®] 435	[30]
Lauric acid	Neopentyl glycol (NPG)	Novozym [®] 435 Novozym [®] 40086	[31]

Table 2.- Viscosity indexes determined according to ASTM D2270 standards applied to the esters obtained in this work.

Ester	Viscosity index
1-hexadecanoyl 2-methylhexanoate	141.58
2-octyl-1-dodecanoyl 2-methylhexanoate	204.28
1,10-decanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate	196.32
1,12-dodecanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate	187.83

Table 3.- Summary of biolubricants found in the literature that claim viscosity indexes of 200 or higher.

Biolubricant	Viscosity index	Reference
Oleic acid industrial grade	208	[16]
Trioleate of TMP from oleic sunflower oil	221	[38]
di-2-ethylhexyl suberate di-2-ethylbutyl dodecanedioate	216	[39]
Waste cooking oil	220	[40]
Soybean oil	227	
Soybean oil	236	[41]
Refined soybean oil	226	[3]
Waste cooking oil 2-ethylhexyl esters	216	[42]
Vegetable based TMP esters	210	[43]
Soybean fatty acid distillate TMP esters	199	[44]
Ethylhexyl esters of high oleic palm oil	208	[7]
Decyl esters of waste cooking soybean oil	204	

Figure captions

Figure 1.- Conversion variation with time for branched esters synthesis of 2-methylhexanoic acid with five different linear mono hydroxylated alcohols of 8, 10, 12, 14 and 16 carbon atoms. Reaction conditions: 20 g of substrates, 5 % wt. biocatalyst, 70 °C and 350 rpm.

Figure 2.- Conversion variation with time for branched esters synthesis of 2-methylhexanoic acid with three branched alcohols of 8, 9 and 10 carbon atoms. Reaction conditions: 20 g of substrates, 5 % wt. biocatalyst, 70 °C and 350 rpm.

Figure 3.- Conversion variation with time for branched esters synthesis of 2-methylhexanoic acid with three branched alcohols of 12, 16 and 20 carbon atoms. Reaction conditions: 20 g of substrates, 5 % biocatalyst, 70 °C and 350 rpm.

Figure 4.- Conversion variation with time for branched esters synthesis of 2-methylhexanoic acid with four dialcohols of 5, 6, 10 and 12 carbon atoms. Reaction conditions: 20 g of substrates, 5 % wt. biocatalyst, 70 °C and 350 rpm.

Figure 5.- Conversion variation with time for synthesis of (A) 1,10-decanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate, (B) 1,12-dodecanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate and (C) 2-octyl-1-dodecanoyl 2-methylhexanoate, at three different temperatures. Reaction conditions: 20 g of substrates, 5 % wt. biocatalyst and 350 rpm.

Figure 6.- Conversion variation with time for synthesis of (A) 1,10-decanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate, (B) 1,12-dodecanediolyl 2-methylhexanoate and (C) 2-octyl-1-dodecanoyl 2-methylhexanoate, at three different enzyme concentration. Reaction conditions: 20 g of substrates, 80 °C and 350 rpm.